

**ELECTRONIC STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS (E-SIMS)
TOWARDS STUDENTS' ENHANCED PERFORMANCE
IN PHYSICS 10**

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Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (E-SIMS) towards Students' Enhanced Performance in Physics 10

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Abstract

This research study aimed to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of using Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) toward enhancing students' academic performance in Physics for Grade 10 students at San Jose National High School, District II-A, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2023-2024. The study utilized a descriptive method, specifically quantitative research. The data gathering instrument used was the Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) Evaluation Tool for non-printed materials. Based on the findings, there is a fair level of agreement among the experts' 'validation of the eSIMs as shown by the Kappa coefficient of 0.221 This implies that the developed eSIMs for Grade 10 Physics has a high acceptability as regards to content, format, presentation and organization, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information. In addition, the utilization of e-SIMs has a positive impact based on the result of the mean scores of the pretest 9.39 at beginning status and posttest ,19.12. highly proficient level. Participants responded very favorably to the quality and complexity of the intervention, feeling that the materials appropriately conveyed key aspects of the intervention. Suggested improvements included the need to increase interactivity and the use of visual formats as a way to engage all students.

Keywords: *e-SIM, intervention materials, student performance, Physics*

Introduction

Performance of Filipino learners in global assessments of science literacy has always been alarming, and this was confirmed again in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022, where Filipino learners' average in science literacy scores ranked fourth to the last among 81 countries. In the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the Philippines ranked the lowest among the 58 included nations receiving scores in mathematics and in science of 297 and 249.

Furthermore, among 79 nations, Filipino students previously performed the worst in reading comprehension and the second least in science and mathematics. Recently, the Philippines ended up again among the countries, which produced the lowest proficiency for young learners in reading, mathematics, and science in the 2022 PISA rankings.

Additional to this, one of the incoming Education 4.0 trusted mitigation is the use of ICT. Information and Communication Technology is a broad term that refers to various technologies used to create, store, exchange, and use information.

In contemporary society, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) emerges as the predominant avenue for disseminating information. Recognized for its efficacy, ICT significantly enhances modern living by facilitating easy access to a plethora of information including news, guidelines, and factual data. This pivotal role of ICT is underscored by its integration into various sectors, prompting initiatives from institutions like the Department of Education to advance its utilization. Hence, integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the teaching of science education aligns with MATATAG's critical components. By utilizing interactive activities, teachers can make the curriculum more relevant and engaging, fostering students' curiosity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

Furthermore, integrating ICT ensures the accelerated delivery of basic education facilities and services by providing access to devices, internet connectivity, and online resources, enabling students to explore cutting-edge scientific knowledge and collaborate beyond traditional classroom boundaries. This approach creates dynamic and inclusive learning environments, equipping students with the necessary scientific skills to become competent, job-ready, and responsible citizens in a technology-driven society.

From the researcher's viewpoint, employing interactive methods like Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) enables teachers to actively involve students, nurturing curiosity, analytical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. These intervention tools aim to address the distinct learning requirements of students encountering academic challenges. They typically offer extra assistance, exercises, or guidance to aid students in understanding fundamental concepts or mastering skills. Integrating intervention resources with regular educational materials proves advantageous as they cater to each student's unique needs, enhancing the educational journey with a tailored approach.

For these reasons, the researcher chose to produce and develop Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) in physical sciences and implemented them to science students to improve learning and fix least mastered skills of the students, thus achieving growth in proficiency level.

Research Questions

This research study aimed to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of using Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs)

toward enhancing students' academic performance in Physics for Grade 10 students at San Jose National High School, District II-A, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2023-2024. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What lessons in Physics 10 could be developed into Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on the five least mastered competencies from the Second Quarter Periodical Test?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) as assessed by expert validators using the LRMDS evaluation tool for non-printed materials described in terms of:
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. format;
 - 2.3. presentation and organization; and
 - 2.4. accuracy and up-to-datedness of information?
3. Is there any significant agreement among the evaluation of the expert validators on the developed eSIMs based on the abovementioned criteria?
4. What is the performance of the Grade 10 students in the pretest and post-test mean scores?
5. Is there a significant difference in the pretest and post-test mean scores of the Grade 10 students in Physics before and after the utilizing the e-SIMs?
6. As perceived by the students, what are the advantages and disadvantages of using the e-SIMs?

Literature Review

Instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning subjects to promote teachers' efficiency and improve students' performance. They make learning more interesting, practical, realistic, and appealing. Gersten et al. (2020) emphasized that instructional materials should include all the tools that the teachers can use to make learning more interesting and memorable.

Tuimur and Chemwei (2020) summarized that if the instructional materials are properly selected and used, the following will occur; learning would be interesting and meaningful, the acquired knowledge will be retained for a longer time, various skills will be acquired by learners, and students will be actively involved in the lesson. Moreover, Physics is a science subject that students often find very difficult, and this is why students always have low achievement in the subject.

SIM was defined by Barredo (2020) as meant to re-teach the concepts and least mastered skills, and in this study the science concepts and skills. It is a material given to students to aid in mastering the competency-based skills which they were not able to develop in regular classroom instructions. According to Borna et al. (2023), Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) is a type of instructional material that is designed to be targeted and effective for students who are struggling with a particular concept or skill. SIM typically includes a variety of activities and resources that are designed to help students learn and master the material.

Similarly, Impas. (2021) mentioned that SIM is important to struggling learners because SIM help in solving perimeter by providing them with targeted support and resources. These materials are designed to address the specific needs of struggling learners and provide effective strategies for improving their performance.

According to the study of Abucejo et al. (2021), the use of SIM has improved the achievement of students in mathematics particularly for the seventh grade level in Zambales National High School in the Philippines. Students using SIM are doing well in mathematics compared to students who do not use SIM in a standardize mathematics test. Another study by Diaz et al. (2020), piloted in the third quarter of 2020 in a private school in Manila, found that the use of SIMs boosted mathematics achievement among Grade 9 students. Students who were provided with SIMs performed better on a standardized mathematics test than those students who did not receive SIMs.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive normative survey was utilized as the research approach in this study. This is fact-finding research with appropriate and correct interpretation (Khan & Soomro, 2019). It is used to collect demographic data on people's behavior, practices, intentions, beliefs, attitudes, views, judgment, interest, perceptions, and so on, which is then evaluated, structured, and interpreted.

The descriptive normative survey was used to assess the differences in student respondents' perception of the utilization of Strategic Intervention Materials in Physics 10 in terms of cognitive and affective learning domains. A pre-experimental, one-group pretest-posttest design was another study design employed by the researcher. In contrast to the hypothesis that the treatment makes a difference, the variables provide reasonable hypotheses explaining the difference between the pre-test and post-test. The design was utilized by the researcher to assess the effectiveness of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials in Physics 10 as applied and used by the students.

Respondents

Purposive sampling was employed for this study to ensure that participants were Grade 10 students from San Jose National High School

during the school year 2023-2024 and are relevant for the evaluation of the material developed. The sampled individuals have been chosen because of their grade level and by school in such a way that they are identical to and refer exclusively to the sampled population. In addition, 30 students from each of the five different classes make the samples of the study.

Instrument

The LRMSD evaluation tool, the 25-item pretest and posttest, and the e-SIMS are the tools to be used in the study. The LRMSD evaluation tool was designed with input from educational experts and follows guidelines to assess the quality of educational materials, focusing on content, format, presentation, organization, and accuracy. It is a standardized tool of the Department of Education used to assess learning materials. The pretest and posttest items were developed based on the learning competencies of the Physics curriculum for Grade 10 students, ensuring relevance and alignment with the e-SIMS content. The e-SIMS themselves will be created to target specific learning objectives, using interactive and multimedia elements to engage students and enhance their understanding of Physics concepts.

Procedure

The researcher strictly followed the guidelines for remote data collection. The study protocol was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDO) and the School Principal to request permission to conduct the study. The SDO of SDO-Antipolo, and the School Principal approved the study. Using the development of e-SIMS as a trigger, the researchers gained the active attention of the participants through orientation. Developmental trajectory of the study Guided by the principle of utility maximization, an infusion of logic and reasoning led the researchers to develop e-SIMS that would be validated by the School Quality Assurance Team through the LRMSD evaluation tool.

When the teacher gave out the consent forms for the research, the students were told that because they were a minor, she needed their signature and their parents' signature in order for them to participate in the experiment. Once the teacher had received the last signed form, to determine how well these supplemental materials worked, she gave the students a pretest that determined the students' knowledge of science prior to treatment. Once she collected the results of the pretest so that she went through the supplemental materials with the students approximately once every week in science time. When the treatment was conducted, then a posttest was administered to check the improvement of the students. The data collection and statistical analysis of the data also started at this point. Also, the post-experimental interviews with the respondents were conducted.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting the study by collaborating with the respondents, the researcher went over and explained the objective of the study. Along with a letter encouraging respondents to complete the necessary questionnaire voluntarily and thoroughly, the researcher also provided a consent document for the study. The data collected from the respondents would remain the most private and confidential and only be utilized for the purpose of the study. As such, the researcher had considered protecting the privacy of the respondents and others. This was done in compliance with RA 10173, also referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Results and Discussion

Lessons in Physics 10 that were developed into Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMS)

Table 1. *Least Mastered Competencies in the Second Quarter of Science 10*

SECOND PERIODICAL TEST				GRADE LEVEL		TEN	
				NO OF LEARNERS		1649	
No.	COMPETENCIES	No of Items	Test Placement	TSO	ASO	%	RANK
1	Compare the relative wavelengths of different forms of electromagnetic waves	12	1,2,3,4,5,6,8,37,38,39,40	19788	9681	48.9236	6
2	Cite examples of practical applications of the different regions of EM waves such as the use of radio waves in telecommunications.	12	9 to 20	19788	11528	58.2575	1
3	Explain the effects of EM radiations on living things and the environment	6	21-24, 41,42	9894	5581	56.4079	2
4	Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	6	43-48	9894	3933	39.7514	8
5	Apply ray diagramming techniques in describing the characteristics and positions of images formed by lenses	6	55-60	9894	5521	55.8015	3
6	Identify ways in which the properties of mirrors and lenses determine their use in optical instruments (e.g., cameras and binoculars)	6	25-30	9894	4691	47.4126	7
7	Demonstrate the generation of electricity by movement of a magnet through a coil	6	49-54	9894	4993	50.4649	5
	Explain the operation of a simple electric motor and generator	6	31-36	9894	5282	53.3859	4

Table 1 indicates that the following competencies are among the least learned in the subject: (1) Citing examples of practical applications of the different regions of electromagnetic (EM) waves, such as the use of radio waves in telecommunication; (2) Explaining the effects of EM radiations on living things and the environment; (3) Applying ray diagramming techniques to describe the characteristics and positions of images formed by lenses; (4) Explaining the operation of a simple electric motor and generator; and (5) Demonstrating the generation of electricity by moving a magnet through a coil.

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIMs) as Assessed Using the LRMDS Evaluation Tool for Non-Printed Materials

Table 2. *Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIMs) as Assessed Using the LRMDS Evaluation Tool for Non-Print Materials*

Content	Validator 1	Validator 2	Validator 3	Mean Score	Remarks
Factor 1	28	28	28	28.00	Passed

Note: Passing Rate for Factor 1 – at least 21 points out of 28 points.

Factor 1, which focused on content, received a maximum score of 28 points, marking it as "PASSED." This indicates a comprehensive and highly satisfactory evaluation suitable for the learners' level of development. It contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the Blocks of time of the grade level for which it is intended, providing for the development of different domains such as physical, fine motor, self-help, expressive, receptive, cognitive, and socio-emotional aspects. Furthermore, it is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices. Additionally, it enhances the development of desirable values and traits, has the potential to arouse interest in storytelling, and provides adequate warnings or symbols in topics and activities where safety and health are concerns.

Table 3. *Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIMs) as Assessed Using the LRMDS Evaluation Tool for Non-Print Materials*

Format	Validator 1	Validator 2	Validator 3	Mean Score	Remarks
Factor 2	70	72	71	71.00	Passed

One validator rated the material as satisfactory under Factor 2: Format, specifically noting its cultural relevance, which is one of the descriptors in the criteria of Illustrations. On the other hand, two out of three validators rated the material as satisfactory for Factor 2: Format, highlighting its adequate illustration in relation to text. As a result, the remarks indicate that the material has passed this evaluation criterion.

Table 4. *Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIMs) as Assessed Using the LRMDS Evaluation Tool for Non-Print Materials*

Presentation and Organization	Validator 1	Validator 2	Validator 3	Mean Score	Remarks
Factor 3	19	20	20	19.67	Passed

One of the validators rated the material as satisfactory under Factor 3, which pertains to the logical and smooth flow of ideas, thereby enhancing the expressive capabilities in either their mother tongue or English language under Factor 3: Presentation and Organization. This evaluation resulted in a rating of "Passed." This indicates that the material successfully meets the criteria set forth for Factor 3, demonstrating coherence and clarity in presenting ideas and facilitating language development in both the native language and English.

Table 5. *Level of Acceptability of the Developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIMs) as Assessed Using the LRMDS Evaluation Tool for Non-Print Materials*

Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information	Validator 1	Validator 2	Validator 3	Mean Score	Remarks
Factor 4	24	24	24	24.00	Passed

For Factor 4, which pertains to the accuracy and up-to-dateness of information, all validators unanimously awarded it the perfect score of 24, resulting in a "Passed" evaluation. This indicates that the material excels in providing precise and current information. It reflects a commendable standard of accuracy, ensuring that learners have access to reliable and relevant content. Moreover, the unanimous agreement among validators underscores the consistency and reliability of this assessment, reinforcing the credibility of the evaluation process.

Table 6. *Cohen's Unweighted kappa*

Ratings	Unweighted kappa	SE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Average kappa	0.159			
Validator 1 - Validator 2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Validator 1 - Validator 3	0.478	0.306	-0.121	1.000
Validator 2 - Validator 3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Validator 1 and Validator 2 showed no agreement ($\kappa = 0.000$), indicating potential discrepancies in their assessments, Validator 1 and Validator 3 demonstrated moderate agreement ($\kappa = 0.478$). Conversely, Validator 2 and Validator 3 also showed no agreement ($\kappa = 0.000$). These differences suggest potential inconsistencies in validators' level of acceptability on the eSIM's Content and Format.

Table 7. *The Fleiss' kappa*

Ratings	Fleiss' kappa	SE	95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Overall	0.221	0.096	-0.565	-0.226
3	-	0.096	0.032	0.41
4	-	0.096	-0.579	-0.201

The value of acceptability of developed e-SIMs cannot be underestimated. The fact that, even in the development stage, e-SIM is acceptable by the majority of respondents shows its reliability and appropriateness for use as additional teaching materials in the learning environment.

Academic Performance of Grade 10 Students in Physics Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs)

Table 8. *Performance of Student-Participants from 10-A Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores*

Score	Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		f	%	F	%
0-17	Beginning	30	100	0	0.00
18-19	Developing	0	0	3	10.00
20-21	Proficient	0	0	8	26.67
22-23	Highly Proficient	0	0	14	46.67
24-25	Advanced	0	0	6	20.00

Table 8 shows the academic performance of student-participants from 10- A before and after the use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs). Before the use of the e-SIM, all 30 student-participants from 10- A were classified as "Beginning" with scores ranging from 0 to 17 in the pretest, indicating a low level of proficiency. After the intervention, significant improvements were observed in their posttest scores. None of the students remained in the "Beginning" category, indicating a 100% improvement rate. Instead, 3 students (10.00%) moved to the "Developing" category, 8 students (26.67%) reached the "Proficient" level, 14 students (46.67%) achieved "Highly Proficient" status, and 6 students (20.00%) advanced to the "Advanced" level. This shift in performance levels demonstrates the positive impact of the e-SIM on student learning outcomes for 10- A.

Table 9. *Performance of Student-Participants from 10 - B Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores*

Score	Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		F	%	f	%
0-17	Beginning	30	100	0	0.00
18-19	Developing	0	0	5	16.67
20-21	Proficient	0	0	9	30.00
22-23	Highly Proficient	0	0	13	43.33
24-25	Advanced	0	0	3	10.00

Table 9 shows the academic performance of student-participants from 10 – B. Prior to the intervention, all 30 student-participants from 10- B were classified as "Beginning," with pretest scores ranging from 0 to 17, indicating a low level of proficiency. Before the use of the e-SIM, all 30 student-participants from 10- A were classified as "Beginning" with scores ranging from 0 to 17 in the pretest, indicating a low level of proficiency. After the intervention, significant improvements were observed in their posttest scores. This shift in performance levels demonstrates the positive impact of the e-SIM on student learning outcomes for 10 – B. 43% Or 13 out of 30 are highly proficient status.

Table 10 shows the academic performance of student-participants from 10 – C. Prior to the intervention, all 30 student-participants from 10- C were classified as "Beginning," with pretest scores ranging from 0 to 17, indicating a low level of proficiency. After the intervention, significant improvements were observed in their posttest scores. None of the students remained in the "Beginning" category, indicating a 100% improvement rate.

Instead, 2 students (6.67%) moved to the "Developing" category, 8 students (26.67%) reached the "Proficient" level, 13 students (43.33%) achieved "Highly Proficient" status, and 7 students (23.33%) advanced to the "Advanced" level. This shift in performance levels demonstrates the positive impact of the e-SIM for the students of 10 – C.

Table 10. Performance of Student-Participants from 10 - C Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores

Score	Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		F	%	f	%
0-17	Beginning	30	100	0	0.00
18-19	Developing	0	0	2	6.67
20-21	Proficient	0	0	8	26.67
22-23	Highly Proficient	0	0	13	43.33
24-25	Advanced	0	0	7	23.33

Table 11 shows the academic performance of student participants from 10 – D. Before the intervention, all 30 student-participants from 10- D were classified as "Beginning," with pretest scores ranging from 0 to 17, indicating a low level of proficiency. After the intervention, significant improvements were observed in their posttest scores. None of the students remained in the "Beginning" category, indicating a 100% improvement rate. Instead, 2 students (6.67%) moved to the "Developing" category, 5 students (16.67%) reached the "Proficient" level, 13 students (43.33%) achieved "Highly Proficient" status, and 10 students (33.33%) advanced to the "Advanced" level. Similar to other sections, there is a great shift in the performance of the students in 10 – D.

Table 11. Performance of Student-Participants from 10 - D Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores

Score	Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		F	%	f	%
0-17	Beginning	30	100	0	0.00
18-19	Developing	0	0	2	6.67
20-21	Proficient	0	0	5	16.67
22-23	Highly Proficient	0	0	13	43.33
24-25	Advanced	0	0	10	33.33

Prior to the intervention, all 30 student-participants from 10- E were classified as "Beginning," with pretest scores ranging from 0 to 17, indicating a low level of proficiency. After the intervention, significant improvements were observed in their posttest scores. None of the students remained in the "Beginning" category, indicating a 100% improvement rate. Instead, 2 students (6.67%) moved to the "Developing" category, 10 students (33.33%) reached the "Proficient" level, 11 students (36.67%) achieved "Highly Proficient" status, and 1 student (3.33%) advanced to the "Advanced" level.

This shift in performance levels demonstrates the positive impact of the e-SIM on student learning outcomes.

Table 12. Performance of Student-Participants from 10 - E Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) based on their Pretest and Posttest Scores

Score	Interpretation	Pretest		Posttest	
		F	%	f	%
0-17	Beginning	30	100	0	0.00
18-19	Developing	0	0	2	6.67
20-21	Proficient	0	0	10	33.33
22-23	Highly Proficient	0	0	11	36.67
24-25	Advanced	0	0	1	3.33

Significant Difference in the Academic Performance of Grade 10 Students in Physics Before and After the Use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs)

Table 13. Test for the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest of 10-A

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	P-Value	Statistical Inference
Pretest	30	8.567	2.012	.0001	Significant
Posttest	30	22.000	1.742		

This significant difference suggests that there was a change in performance from before to after the intervention, with students showing improvement in their scores. The mean score decrease from the pretest to the posttest could indicate several things, such as a decrease in difficulty level, a decrease in motivation or effort, or simply natural variance in the data.

However, given the significant difference, it's likely that the intervention had an effect on the students' performance.

Table 14. *Test for the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest of 10- B*

	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Statistical Inference</i>
Pretest	30	9.567	2.012	.0001	Significant
Posttest	30	21.433	1.716		

The implications of these findings are similar to those discussed for Table 13. The significant difference indicates that the intervention for 10- B was effective in improving student learning outcomes. Educators and policymakers can use this information to refine and improve the intervention for future implementation. Additionally, it highlights the importance of using data-driven approaches to assess the effectiveness of educational interventions.

Table 15. *Test for the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest of 10- C*

	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Statistical Inference</i>
Pretest	30	9.067	2.196	.0001	Significant
Posttest	30	22.300	1.622		

These findings have similar implications to those discussed for Tables 13 and 14. The significant difference indicates that the intervention for 10- C was effective in improving student learning outcomes. This information can be used to refine and improve the intervention for future implementation. Additionally, it underscores the importance of using data-driven approaches to assess the effectiveness of educational interventions.

Table 16. *Test for the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest of 10- D*

	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Statistical Inference</i>
Pretest	30	10.567	2.012	.0001	Significant
Posttest	30	22.600	1.632		

This suggests that the interventions for 10- B, 10- C, and 10- D led to improvements in student performance. These findings have similar implications to those discussed for Tables 13, 14, and 15. The significant difference indicates that the intervention for 10- D was effective in improving student learning outcomes.

Table 17. *Test for the Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest of 10- E*

	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Statistical Inference</i>
Pretest	30	9.200	2.340	.0001	Significant
Posttest	30	22.300	1.622		

These findings have similar implications to those discussed for Tables 13, 14, 15, and 16. The significant difference indicates that the intervention for 10- E was effective in improving student learning outcomes. This information can be used to refine and improve the intervention for future implementation. Additionally, it underscores the importance of using data-driven approaches to assess the effectiveness of educational interventions.

Advantages and Disadvantages of the Employed Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) as Perceived by Students

Enhanced Understanding and Critical Thinking. The Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) on Physics has significantly impacted students' understanding and approach to Physics concepts, media consumption and information processing. Through this eSIMs, students have developed a deeper comprehension of Physics concepts and lessons. They have learned the importance of critical thinking in analyzing information objectively, evaluating its reliability, and considering multiple perspectives before forming opinions or sharing information. This emphasis on critical thinking has made students more cautious in solving problems, leading to a more complex and useful learning. Learner-respondent 1 and 2 stated, respectively, that:

"The Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIM) has been a guide and foundation of my knowledge of difficult Physics lessons. Through it, I have a better understanding of the concepts and importance of physics in solving problems related to the physical aspect of science."

"E-SIMs have helped me to be more critical in learning physics-related information. It has made me more aware and more aware of my surroundings."

Relevance to Daily Life. Another prominent theme is the Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs)'s relevance to students'

daily lives. They found the content meaningful and applicable to their everyday interactions and experiences, suggesting that the eSIMs effectively connected theoretical concepts to practical situations. The eSIMs on Physics have been instrumental in making theoretical concepts relevant and applicable to students' daily lives. By presenting content that directly relates to their experiences and challenges, such as solving problems and inquiries, the eSIMs have helped students see the practical implications of science concepts. Through engagement with real-world scenarios and the development of practical skills, students have learned how to apply physics concepts in their interactions with the world. Learner-respondent 3 and 4 stated that:

"The content of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) has come closer to my reality. They have made sense in my daily life and socializing with others."

"Through Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) my questions about the world are answered. We all know that science has an answer to what is happening around us, and eSIM is an entertaining way to learn it."

Enhanced Engagement and Interest. The responses of the students highlight the positive impact of e-SIMs on students' engagement and interest in learning, particularly in the challenging subject of Physics. Students reported increased activity and interest in their studies, indicating that the use of multimedia resources in education can enhance student motivation and enthusiasm for learning. The use of e-SIMs provides a unique and encouraging experience compared to traditional modules and textbooks, suggesting that multimedia tools can play a significant role in enhancing the learning experience and effectiveness of educational materials. Learner-respondent 4 and 5 stated that:

"Because of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs), I have been more proactive in learning. I was more interested in physics."

"Apart from modules and books, the use of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) is more unique and learning compelling."

Challenges and Suggestions for Improvement of e-SIMs. These responses highlight several challenges faced by students in using e-SIMs, as well as suggestions for improving their effectiveness. One challenge mentioned is the difficulty in understanding certain concepts due to the depth and technicality of some parts of the e-SIMs. This suggests that while multimedia resources can enhance learning, they should be designed in a way that is accessible and understandable to students of varying levels of expertise. Another suggestion is to include more visual aids or multimedia in the modules to facilitate understanding and learning. This aligns with the idea that multimedia resources can enhance the learning experience by providing additional context and explanations that text alone may not convey effectively. Lastly, the need for a reliable device for accessing e-SIMs is mentioned, highlighting the importance of ensuring that students have access to appropriate technology to fully benefit from these materials. Learner-respondent 7, 8 and 9 stated, respectively, that:

"There are parts of Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (e-SIMs) that are so deep and technical that they are difficult to understand. It has been a barrier to me to fully understand some concepts."

"I feel like the module could be improved a lot if it had more visual aids or multimedia to facilitate understanding and learning."

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: The least mastered competencies of the students could serve as bases for the development of e-SIMs to address specific areas where students need the most improvement. The developed e-SIMs in Physics 10 are acceptable in terms of: Content, Format, Presentation and organization; and Accuracy and up-to-datedness of information. Students who utilized the e-SIMs showed improved performance in Physics 10, substantially enhancing students' understanding of Physics concepts and their ability to apply these concepts in real-life situations.

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